

Orthodontic Bone Screws: A Comprehensive Review

Sania Khan¹
 Rakesh Thukral²
 Ashish Garg³
 Kamalshikha Baheti⁴
 Amit Tripathi⁵
 Amit Singh Choudhary⁶

Postgraduate Student¹
 Department Of Orthodontics & Dentofacial Orthopaedics
 Sri Aurobindo College of Dentistry,
 Indore (M.P.), 453555, India

B.D.S., M.D.S²
 Professor,
 Department of Orthodontics & Dentofacial Orthopaedics
 Sri Aurobindo College of Dentistry,
 Indore (M.P.), 453555, India

B.D.S., M.D.S³
 F.P.F.A, F.I.C.D (U.S.A)
 Certified Cleft & Craniofacial Orthodontist
 (Smile Train – U.S.A)
 Diplomate of Indian Board of Orthodontics (D.I.B.O.)
 Professor and Head,
 Department of Orthodontics & Dentofacial Orthopaedics
 Sri Aurobindo College of Dentistry,
 Indore (M.P.), 453555, India

B.D.S., M.D.S⁴
 Professor,
 Department of Orthodontics & Dentofacial Orthopaedics
 Sri Aurobindo College of Dentistry,
 Indore (M.P.), 453555, India

B.D.S., M.D.S⁵
 Reader,
 Department of Orthodontics & Dentofacial Orthopaedics
 Sri Aurobindo College of Dentistry,
 Indore (M.P.), 453555, India

B.D.S., M.D.S⁶
 Senior Lecturer,
 Department of Orthodontics & Dentofacial Orthopaedics
 Sri Aurobindo College of Dentistry,
 Indore (M.P.), 453555, India

Access this article online

Website:

www.updent.in

Quick Response Code:

Corresponding Author:

Dr. Sania Khan
 Postgraduate Student
 Department of Orthodontics &
 Dentofacial Orthopaedics
 Sri Aurobindo College of Dentistry,
 Indore (M.P.), 453555, India

Abstract

In orthodontics, anchorage plays a crucial role in facilitating accomplishment of desired objectives with minimal inadvertent side effects. One of undesirable effects is loss of anchorage. However, introduction of Temporary Anchorage Devices (TADS) has brought about significant advancements in the field of orthodontics. In recent years, Orthodontic Bone Screws (OBS) which are placed into Infra-zygomatic crest of maxilla & Buccal Shelf area of mandible offer an extra-radicular placement modality without requirement for extensive surgical interventions. Notably, OBS have demonstrated significantly reduced failure rates compared to conventional mini-implants. Consequently, OBS have revolutionized orthodontic treatment approaches by providing enhanced stability and efficiency in anchorage, thereby leading to optimal treatment outcomes. This comprehensive review provides an in-depth analysis of the evolutionary progression of orthodontic anchorage systems, with particular emphasis on the transformative impact of Orthodontic Bone Screws. By virtue of their distinctive placement techniques and enhanced stability attributes, Orthodontic Bone Screws have catalyzed remarkable advancements in the field of orthodontics, ultimately leading to the attainment of superior treatment outcomes.

Keywords: Biomechanics of bone screws, biomechanics of micro-implants, BSS, Buccal Shelf area, full arch distalization, Infra-zygomatic crest, IZC, mini-implants, orthodontic bone screws.

Introduction:

Orthodontic treatment relies on achieving stable anchorage to minimize undesired tooth movements and optimize treatment outcomes.⁽¹⁾ Traditional methods have faced challenges in maintaining anchorage, necessitating advance-ments in skeletal anchorage systems. In recent decades, absolute anchorage systems, such as mini-implants or micro-screws, have gained popularity due to their ease of placement and minimally invasive nature. However, early loosening remains a common drawback. Skeletal Anchorage Systems (SAS), like I-plates and Y-plates, offer a more rigid alternative but require extensive surgical intervention.⁽²⁾

In recent years, the development of Infra-zygomatic crest (IZC) & Buccal Shelf (BS) screws has aimed to overcome limitations in traditional mini-screws. These screws, positioned intraorally into basilar bone by penetrating oral mucosa, offer strong osseous anchorage. Lever arm springs anchored with IZC or MBS bone screws effectively manage impaction recovery, while their Extra-alveolar placement facilitates dentition retraction and arch rotation.⁽³⁾

Segmented & full arch distalization using extra-radicular bone screws have revolutionized orthodontics. These techniques offer non-extraction options and effectively address cases with anchorage loss during retreatment. As orthodontic retreatment is increasingly common due to poor mechanics, finding alternative means to rehabilitate clinical situations is imperative. Implementation of Infra-zygomatic crest (IZC) & Buccal Shelf screws (BSS) provides hope while reducing retreatment time. However, careful usage is crucial, considering anatomical limitations, artistic skills, biomechanical perspectives, and potential side effects. This technique requires a comprehensive understanding of these factors for optimal treatment outcomes.⁽²⁾

A Brief Review of Literature:

Edward H. Angle⁽⁴⁾ introduced the idea of stationary anchorage leading to enhancement of Extra-oral anchorage systems. Gainsforth et al. (1945)⁽⁵⁾ began the era of skeletal anchorage. Leonard Linkow (1969)⁽⁶⁾ used endosseous implants for using Class II elastics for retraction of maxillary incisors. Branemark (1970s)⁽⁷⁾ noticed efficacious osseo integration of implants into bone, after that numerous

Orthodontists amplified their curiosity in implants for Orthodontic anchorage. Creekmore et al. (1983)⁽⁸⁾ implanted vitallium surgical bone screws beneath spina nasalis for anchoring upper incisor intrusion.

Erick J.W. Liou et al. (2007)⁽⁹⁾ measured the Infra-zygomatic crest thickness to guide the safe insertion of miniscrews without damaging the maxillary first molar root. Eric Liou (2017)⁽¹⁰⁾ recommended using the Infra-zygomatic crest for temporary anchorage devices, particularly above the mesiobuccal or distobuccal roots of the second molar (U7). The Ortho Bone Screw (OBS) by OrthoBoneScrew®, developed by Dr. Eric Liou, is commonly used for these procedures. HaiboLiu et al. (2019)⁽¹¹⁾ used CBCT to assess the mandibular buccal shelf (MBS) anatomy and determine the optimal region for miniscrew implantation for mandibular dentition distalization. They found that the L6db-L7mb region (distobuccal root of first molar and mesiobuccal root of second molar) is preferred choice for miniscrew insertion in the Buccal Shelf region for mandibular dental segment retraction.

Design of Orthodontic Bone Screws:

Elements of Implant Design:

1. Choice of material
2. Design of the head portion
3. Dimensions of Bone screw

1. Choice of material:

Fracture resistance is especially important for Bone screws since they are often implanted in DI (>1250 HU) grade bone (IZC & BS regions).⁽²⁾ Stainless steel's superior **resistance to fracture** makes it the material of choice over Ti alloy.

2. Design of the head portion:

Mushroom shape design of head portion is the most common.⁽²⁾ (Figure. 1)

Figure 1. Design of head portion of Bone screws.

3. Dimensions of Bone Screw:

The Bone screws used in Orthodontics typically have diameter of 2mm & are obtainable in lengths of 10mm, 12mm, & 14mm. For optimal stability, a minimum bone length of 8 mm is required. (Table 1)

Table 1. Dimensions of Orthodontic Bone screws:

S. No.	Location (Extra- alveolar)	Screw	Screw Diameter (mm)	Screw Length (mm)
1	Maxilla (Thick soft tissue)	IZC	2	14
2	Maxilla (Thin soft tissue)	IZC	2	12
3	Mandible	BSS	2	10

Placement of Bone screws:

Implants with larger diameters and longer lengths can withstand a higher fracture torque making them resistant to torsional fracture and are preferable for Extra alveolar (E-A) locations.⁽¹²⁾ When these implants are to be put in a region of dense bone (cortical bone), it may be necessary to perform a first puncture using spear-tip or clinical probe. This is evident even while utilizing self-drilling orthodontic steel implants. Reducing potential for fracture during implantation is the primary goal of this treatment.⁽¹³⁾ According to research by Motoyoshi et al., drilling a pilot hole, in cortical bone prior to implant insertion may improve main stability of mini-implants into adolescents.⁽¹⁴⁾

Placement of Infrazygomatic Crest Screw:

When inserting a bone screw into the IZC, the angle of insertion is crucial. Park et al.⁽¹⁵⁾ correlated angle between mini-implant's axis & cortical bone, and they found that when axis is virtually parallel to long root axis of molars, implant has a larger contact area with the bone. When the screw is positioned vertically, it has less of a likelihood of reaching root. For placement of Infrazygomatic crest screw:

1. The surgical area is anesthetized.
2. Self-drilling screw point is positioned at 90° angle to bone surface into area of Infra-zygomatic crest (IZC).
3. Screws are often placed between upper first & second molars in adults & upper second premolar & first molar in young patients, with point of screw penetrating 1mm in cortical bone at height of buccal roots.
4. Bone screw driver is turned clockwise while rotating it between 60°-70° towards the occlusal plane, effectively threading the bone screw into the bone.

Placement of Buccal Shelf Screw:

Nucera et al.⁽¹⁶⁾ & Elshebiny et al.⁽¹⁷⁾ described optimal anatomic position for placement is 4–8mm distal to cement-enamel junction upon buccal aspect of root of lower second molar.

Significant morphological variation exists in this area, with some patients having well-demarcated bone plateaus while others have straighter profiles. Diagnosis through palpation or CBCT helps identify these differences and guides appropriate implant placement. Placement of the implant is simplified for individuals who have a distinct plateau and healthy, attached gingiva; a sizable Buccal Shelf (BS) enables the implants to be placed into virtually vertical position, practically parallel to root of lower molars.

Technique for implantation is similar to that used for IZC implants; i.e., after abiding biosafety guidelines, local anesthetic is administered, & cortical bone is drilled. The implant is then positioned at ideal angle (70 degrees) with respect to occlusal plane. Based upon biomechanics, implants may be angled mesially in certain cases.⁽¹³⁾

A single bone screw can handle up to 300-350 g of force, allowing for immediate loading.⁽²⁾

Biomechanics of Bone screws:

a. Infrazygomatic crest Screw

Incisor torque control might be impacted with alterations in force geometry, such as those instigated by change in hooks or power arm located into anterior region of arch, and also by variations in vertical heights (open or deep bite).⁽¹⁸⁾ In addition, the potential inclination of occlusal plane must be taken into account when using asymmetrical forces to rectify Class II subdivision using mini-implants in IZC. Attention should be paid to precise application of the forces' path of action in the case of asymmetrical treatments of midline abnormalities. The intended kind of motion will be determined by the height and placement of anterior hook/power arm. Clinically, such differential motions may be re-produced upon anterior teeth using mechanics utilising extra-alveolar mini-implants by adjusting force line of action, via variations in length of hooks/power arms. Park et al⁽¹⁹⁾ emphasized the need for archwires with long hooks to be employed throughout full maxillary dentition retraction for generating lingual root torque for incisors.

b. Buccal Shelf Screw

Entire mandibular dentition can be retracted at once with this mechanism because the screws are placed outside roots' line of action and do not hinder the retraction of entire arch (with exception of third molars, which must be extracted).

Roberts et al⁽²⁰⁾ analysed using finite elements (3D) and cone beam computed tomography (CBCT) showed existence of stable, "statically determinate" system resulting from mechanics for retracting the entire mandibular dentition; this was accomplished by placing 2 mini-implants in the Buccal Shelf (BS) & full-size rectangular archwire, with NiTi springs applying a constant force of 200g. As retraction force in whole arch produces an intrusive force in molars & extruding force in incisors due to rotation of mandibular arch, this system is an excellent resource for a conservative & non-extraction treatment of Class-III malocclusion with anterior open bite. Open bite closure & simultaneous Class-III correction were favored by this counterclockwise rotation of mandibular plane, as measured by finite elements analysis, which caused 3-mm molar intrusion & 2-mm incisor extrusion.

Clinical applications of Bone Screws:

1. Camouflaging a Class II & Class III malocclusion by distalization of the maxillary and mandibular dentition,
2. Re-treatment cases involving loss of anchorage often require the distalization of dental arches, which can be challenging using conventional orthodontic mechanics.⁽²⁾
3. In adjunct with Clear aligners: Clear aligners have revolutionized orthodontic treatment for various malocclusions.⁽²¹⁾ Bone screws provide reliable anchorage for managing challenging malocclusions, such as scissors-bite discrepancies and full buccal cross-bites.
4. Molar uprighting.
5. Recovery of impacted teeth.
6. Segmental distalization.
7. Single-tooth intrusion into full-arch tooth arch.

Contraindications:

1. Pan systemic conditions
2. Psychological disorders.
3. Periodontal infections.
4. Neoplastic lesions.
5. Poor bone quality or inadequate space.
6. Oral mucosal disorders.

Risks & Complications:

Most unfavorable effects of clinical usage of bone screw anchorage is screw breakage that may happen either during installation or removal. There are a number of possible causes of screw failure, but close proximity of screw and root is the most prevalent. Damage to soft tissues heals quickly, while damage to hard tissues cannot be repaired and must be avoided at all costs. Bone screw anchoring comes with its own set of hazards and difficulties, so it's important to be aware of them and exercise caution while applying them.⁽²²⁾

Advantages of Bone Screws:

OBSs, placed in IZC & BS regions, provide secure anchorage with stable bone and high density. Made of stainless steel, these screws offer excellent biocompatibility, mechanical characteristics, corrosion & stress resistivity.⁽²³⁾ Their unique features, including a mushroom-shaped head and double-neck design, enhance patient comfort, elastic chain retention, hygiene control, and allow for additional attachments.⁽²⁴⁾ The use of OBSs results in shorter treatment time, reliable anchorage, and reduced reliance on patient cooperation. They effectively correct crowding by retracting buccal segments and increasing arch length without the need for tooth extraction.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, orthodontic bone screws (OBSs) have emerged as a valuable tool in modern orthodontic treatment. Their placement in infra-zygomatic crest (IZC) & buccal shelf (BS) regions offers stable anchorage with favorable bone quality and density.

While OBSs present advantages such as enhanced treatment efficiency, less patient cooperation, and precise control over tooth movement, it is crucial to be aware of the associated risks, such as screw fracture and soft tissue irritation. Proper placement techniques, pre-drilling, and attention to hygiene control are essential to minimize complications and ensure successful outcomes. Despite the documented benefits of OBSs, their incorporation into routine clinical practice has been relatively limited. Raising awareness and increasing comfort levels among orthodontists regarding OBS utilization may lead to broader adoption and improved treatment outcomes for challenging cases.

Bibliography:

1. Nanda R. Biomechanics in clinical orthodontics. WB Saunders company; 1996.
2. Ghosh A. Infra-zygomatic crest and buccal shelf-orthodontic bone screws: a leap ahead of micro-implants—clinical perspectives. *J Indian Orthod Soc.* 2018;52(4_suppl2):127–41.
3. Chang CH, Lin LY, Roberts WE. Orthodontic bone screws: A quick update and its promising future. *Orthod Craniofac Res.* 2021;24:75–82.
4. Fox J. Weinberger, BW: Orthodontics; a Historical Review of its Origin and Evolution, St. Louis; 1926.
5. Gainsforth BL, Higley LB. A study of orthodontic anchorage possibilities in basal bone. *Am J Orthod Oral Surg.* 1945;31(8):406–17.
6. Linkow LI. The endosseous blade implant and its use in orthodontics. *Int J Orthod.* 1969;18:149–54.
7. Brånemark PI, Breine U, Adell R, Hansson BO, Lindström J, Ohlsson Å. Intra-osseous anchorage of dental prostheses: I. Experimental studies. *Scand J Plast Reconstr Surg.* 1969;3(2):81–100.
8. Creekmore TD. The possibility of skeletal anchorage. *J Clin Orthod.* 1983;17:266–9.
9. Liou EJ, Chen PH, Wang YC, Lin JCY. A computed tomographic image study on the thickness of the infrazygomatic crest of the maxilla and its clinical implications for miniscrew insertion. *Am J Orthod Dentofacial Orthop.* 2007;131(3):352–6.
10. Hsu E, Lin JSY, Yeh HY, Chang C, Robert E. Comparison of the failure rate for infrazygomatic bone screws placed in movable mucosa or attached gingiva. *Int J Orthod Implant.* 2017;47(1):96–106.
11. Liu H, Wu X, Tan J, Li X. Safe regions of miniscrew implantation for distalization of mandibular dentition with CBCT. *Prog Orthod.* 2019;20(1):1–8.
12. Chang C, Liu SS, Roberts WE. Primary failure rate for 1680 extra-alveolar mandibular buccal shelf mini-screws placed in movable mucosa or attached gingiva. *Angle Orthod.* 2015;85(6):905–10.
13. Nanda R, Uribe FA, Yadav S. Temporary anchorage devices in orthodontics e-book. Elsevier Health Sciences; 2019.
14. Motoyoshi M, Matsuoka M, Shimizu N. Application of orthodontic mini-implants in adolescents. *Int J Oral Maxillofac Surg.* 2007;36(8):695–9.
15. Park HS, Jeong SH, Kwon OW. Factors affecting the clinical success of screw implants used as orthodontic anchorage. *Am J Orthod Dentofacial Orthop.* 2006;130(1):18–25.
16. Nucera R, Lo Giudice A, Bellocchio AM, Spinuzza P, Caprioglio A, Perillo L, et al. Bone and cortical bone thickness of mandibular buccal shelf for miniscrew insertion in adults. *Angle Orthod.* 2017;87(5):745–51.
17. Elshebiny T, Palomo JM, Baumgaertel S. Anatomic assessment of the mandibular buccal shelf for miniscrew insertion in white patients. *Am J Orthod Dentofacial Orthop.* 2018;153(4):505–11.
18. Almeida MR. Biomechanics of extra-alveolar mini-implants. *Dent Press J Orthod.* 2019;24:93–109.
19. Park HS, Bae SM, Kyung HM, Sung JH. Simultaneous incisor retraction and distal molar movement with microimplant anchorage. *World J Orthod.* 2004;5(2).
20. Roberts WE, Viecilli RF, Chang C, Katona TR, Paydar NH. Biology of biomechanics: Finite element analysis of a statically determinate system to rotate the occlusal plane for correction of a skeletal Class III open-bite malocclusion. *Am J Orthod Dentofacial Orthop.* 2015;148(6):943–55.
21. Papadimitriou A, Mousoulea S, Gkantidis N, Kloukos D. Clinical effectiveness of Invisalign® orthodontic treatment: a systematic review. *Prog Orthod.* 2018;19(1):1–24.
22. Kuroda S, Tanaka E. Risks and complications of miniscrew anchorage in clinical orthodontics. *Jpn Dent Sci Rev.* 2014;50(4):79–85.
23. Sandeep S, Katheesa P. An overview of extra alveolar bone screws-IZC/BS screws. *Biomedicine.* 2020;40(2):108–10.
24. Park JH. Temporary anchorage devices in clinical orthodontics. John Wiley & Sons; 2020.